

New records for the Heteroptera (Hemiptera) fauna of Ankara province

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ABSTRACT: This study was carried out based on Heteroptera (Hemiptera) samples collected in various locations of Kahramankazan district of Ankara province between April and November 2022.

Codophila maculicollis (Dallas, 1851), *Apodyphus amygdali* (Germar, 1817), *Holcogaster fibulata* (Germar, 1831) and *Oncotylus (Oncotylus) punctipes* Reuter, 1875 species, which were previously reported in Türkiye, were recorded for the first time from Ankara, and *O. punctipes* was also new record for the central Anatolia region in this study.

KEY WORDS: Heteroptera, fauna of Ankara province (Türkiye), contribution

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INTRODUCTION

The Heteroptera (Hemiptera) suborder, with more than 45,000 species known worldwide, includes terrestrial, semi-aquatic, and aquatic species.

More than 9,365 species belonging to 1,632 genera are distributed in the Palaearctic Region (Aukema et al., 2013, Henry, 2017; Fent & Dursun, 2022).

Many Heteroptera species have been found in Türkiye (Kıyak, 2019) and it has been reported that there are 1650 species in total (Çerçi and Koçak, 2023).

The Pentatomidae Leach, 1815 and Miridae Hahn, 1833 families are of economic importance and are among the largest families of the Heteroptera suborder.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

The specimens included in this study were collected in different localities in the Kahramankazan district of Ankara from April to November 2022.

Heteroptera specimens were collected with a swap net, killed in containers containing 70% alcohol, and then prepared in accordance with the standards of the zoological museum.

Identification of species was made with the help of comparison material and literature.

Identification of species was done under a stereo microscope and using the keys of Stichel (1955-1962) and Wagner (1970/71).

In this study, locality records of 4 species identified as a result of the evaluation of Pentatomidae and Miridae species are presented.

In addition to the Türkiye distributions (Önder et al., 2006; Fent & Dursun, 2022; Yazıcı et al., 2014; Yıldırım & Yazıcı, 2016) of the species, the Palaearctic distributions are given from Aukema (1995-2013).

RESULTS

In this study, four species belonging to two families of the suborder Heteroptera were identified. The results of the study are given below:

Family: Pentatomidae Leach, 1815

Genus: *Codophila* Mulsant & Rey, 1866

Codophila maculicollis (Dallas, 1851)

Material examined: Ankara: Kahramankazan, Durasan Şah Nature Park, (1285 m) 40°15'54.0" N 32°35'38.1"E, 06.11.2022, 1 ♂.

Distribution in Türkiye: Artvin, Bilecik, Denizli, Erzincan, Erzurum, Isparta, Kars, Tunceli (Yazıcı et al., 2014).

General Distribution: North Africa: Algeria, Egypt, Libya, Morocco, Tunisia. Asia: Afghanistan, Asian Türkiye, China (NW)?, Iran, Israel, Jordan, Saudi Arabia, Sinai, Syria, Yemen. Extralimital: Ethiopia, India, Sudan (Aukema, 1995-2013; Fent & Dursun, 2022).

Genus: *Apodiphus* Spinosula, 1837

Apodiphus amygdali (Germar, 1817)

Material examined: Ankara: Kahramankazan, around Ahi Koca stream (905 m); 40°13'08.6"N 32°45'01.9"E; 28 13.08.2022, 1 ♂.

Distribution in Türkiye: Çanakkale, Edirne, İstanbul, Tekirdağ, Adana, Adıyaman, Antalya, Artvin, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bayburt, Bingöl, Burdur, Bursa, Çorum, Denizli, Diyarbakır, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Gaziantep, Hatay, Iğdır, Isparta, İçel, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Kars, Kayseri, Kilis, Konya, Malatya, Manisa, Mardin, Mersin, Muğla, Osmaniye, Rize, Şanlıurfa, Tokat, Tuncel, (Fent & Dursun, 2022).

General Distribution: Albania, Bosnia Hercegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, European Türkiye, Greece, Italy, Macedonia, Montenegro, Serbia, Armenia, Asian Türkiye, Azerbaijan, Georgia, Iran, Iraq, Israel, Lebanon, Syria, Turkmenistan (Aukema, 1995-

2013; Fent & Dursun, 2022).

Genus: *Holcogaster* Fieber, 1861

***Holcogaster fibulata* (Germar, 1831)**

Material examined: Ankara: Kahraman-kazan Susuz (914 m); 40°01'14.4"N 32°38'58.0"E; 29.10.2022, 1♀, 4♂♂.

Distribution in Türkiye: Tekirdağ, İstanbul Kırklareli, Adana, Amasya, Antalya, Balıkesir, Burdur, Çanakkale, Çorum, Elazığ, Eskişehir, Gaziantep, Hatay, Isparta, İçel, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karaman, Kastamonu, Manisa, Mersin, Muğla, Niğde, Sakarya, Samsun, Sinop, Sivas, Tekirdağ, Tokat (Fent & Dursun, 2022).

General Distribution: Albania, Belgium, Bulgaria, Crete, Croatia, European Türkiye, France, Germany, Greece, Italy, Macedonia, Montenegro, Netherlands, Portugal, Spain, Switzerland, Algeria, Canary Islands, Libya, Morocco, Tunisia, Asian Türkiye, Cyprus, Iraq, Israel, Syria. Note: According to Fent and Dursun (2022), this species was previously given as *Holcogaster exilis* by some authors.

Family: Miridae Hahn, 1833

Genus: *Oncotylus* (Fieber, 1858)

***Oncotylus (Oncotylus) punctipes* Reuter, 1875**

Material examined: Ankara: Kahraman-kazan, Bitik neighbourhood; 40°07'43.0"N 32°36'28.6"E (853 m) 39, 24.09.2022, 1♀.

Distribution in Türkiye: Ağrı, Erzurum, Kütahya (Önder et al., 2006; Yıldırım & Yazıcı, 2016).

General Distribution: Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Byelorussia, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Moldavia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia (CT NT ST), Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden, Ukraine, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Türkiye, Georgia, Russia (ES WS), Uzbekistan (Aukema, 1995-2013).

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